

Using Torque and RPM loss to estimate the presence of icing clouds with UAVs

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Introduction

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs), more commonly known as drones, have emerged as important tools, across numerous industries, from delivery and agriculture to disaster response and environmental monitoring. However, adverse weather conditions, particularly icing, present a significant operational challenge. Icing not only reduces aerodynamic efficiency but also increases mechanical strain, leading to potential flight instability and mission failure. Understanding how UAVs respond to icing conditions is critical for developing mitigation strategies that enhance their reliability and safety.

This research project focuses on the automation of drones to monitor rotational speed (RPM) and torque loss when traversing cloudy and icing conditions. As drone technology advances, their deployment in various sectors, including delivery services and environmental monitoring, rapidly increases. However, adverse weather conditions, particularly icing, stand to affect drone performance and safety.

Conducted as part of the MC REU Summer Research program with the Vertical Lift Research Center of Excellence, this study follows a problem-based and experimental learning approach. By iteratively developing and testing solutions, the project seeks to improve drone performance in harsh environments. Autonomous drones equipped with advanced sensors and data analysis algorithms are used to measure the impact of cloud and icing conditions on propulsion. The Han-Palacios correlation is applied to estimate the volume of water within clouds and assess general icing severity based on torque loss. As soon as ice starts to form, thrust decreases, making it difficult for an autonomous UAV to maintain speed or altitude.

This loss of torque and degradation in RPM directly correlate with ice formation on the propellers. Monitoring these metrics offers a better understanding of cloud characteristics, such as liquid water content and mean volume diameter of droplets. The expected outcome of this study includes a dataset of torque loss and RPM degradation values for UAV icing conditions, enabling the refinement of predictive models. Additionally, the research evaluates cost-effective sensing technologies, such as off-the-shelf light detection and ranging (LiDAR) systems, for detecting cloud properties. Data is collected using onboard Odroid computers and a Pixhawk flight controller, with analysis based on the Han-Palacios correlation. For future work we aim to work on developing robust real-time data processing algorithms and exploring lightweight, affordable mitigation strategies for icing effects to improve UAV reliability.

Literature Review

1. Historical Context of Icing Research

Aircraft icing has been a major challenge for aviation safety and performance, prompting extensive research over the decades. The historical development of icing studies is well documented

in *We Freeze to Please: A History of NASA's Icing Research Tunnel*^[3], which outlines how NASA's Icing Research Tunnel (IRT) played a critical role in advancing our understanding of ice formation and mitigation strategies. Early efforts focused on wind tunnel testing and empirical observations, evolving into sophisticated computational models and experimental validation techniques.

2. Experimental and Theoretical Approaches to Icing Detection

A key study on performance degradation due to icing^[2] presents an empirical model for estimating liquid water content (LWC) and mean volume diameter (MVD) using torque variations. The study used controlled icing chamber experiments to validate the Han-Palacios Correlation (HPC), demonstrating its effectiveness in predicting torque degradation. The Blade Element Momentum Theory (BEMT) was used to analyze ice accumulation and its effects on aerodynamic forces, showing a direct correlation between icing severity and torque loss.

3. Application of Torque and RPM Loss in UAV Icing Detection

Expanding on these findings, the use of torque and RPM loss for UAV icing detection presents a cost-effective alternative. This method leverages changes in rotor performance metrics to estimate ice accretion severity, reducing dependency on expensive and power-intensive onboard sensors. The application of the Han-Palacios Correlation in UAVs allows for real-time monitoring of rotor efficiency and early warning of icing conditions, which can help prevent accidents by correcting or adjusting the flight path to better account for patches of such clouds. However, limitations exist in accurately estimating mean volume diameter (MVD) due to inherent uncertainties in real-world applications, which goes to show how better empirical models and field testing are needed in ideal icing conditions.

4. Alternative Sensing Methods: LIDAR-Based Environmental Sensing

A study on Imaging LIDARs for Space Applications discusses high-resolution, three-dimensional scanning LIDARs^[1] and their ability to identify atmospheric particles and hazards. LIDAR-based sensing could theoretically be adapted for UAV icing detection by identifying ice particles in clouds before accretion occurs. However, challenges such as size, power consumption, and integration feasibility limit its practical application for small UAVs at this stage.

Conclusion

The study of aircraft icing has progressed from early wind tunnel experiments to sophisticated computational models, leading to significant advancements in detection and mitigation techniques. Leveraging torque and RPM loss as a cost-effective method for UAV icing detection offers a viable alternative to traditional sensors, reducing the need for expensive equipment. While empirical models like the Han-Palacios Correlation demonstrate promising results, further refinement is necessary to enhance predictive accuracy and ensure real-world applicability. Future research should prioritize improving empirical modeling methods and conducting extensive field tests to improve UAV safety and reliability in challenging icing conditions.

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